

Consortium Agreement

Between: Deutsche Zentralbibliothek für Medizin (ZB MED)- Informationszentrum Lebenswissenschaften, Gleueler Str. 60, 50931 Cologne, represented by its Management Board, and Journal of Medical Insight (JOMI), Inc.

Effective Date: 1st August 2025

Purpose

ZB MED will lead a German consortium that provides participating German institutions access to JOMI content (videos and full-text articles) under a licensing arrangement. JOMI offers these benefits at the agreed consortium price structure.

2. Scope & Term

- **Term:** January 1, 2026 – December 31, 2028 (three years)
- **Eligible Institutions:** Participating publicly or privately funded German universities, research institutions, libraries, hospitals (per ZB MED eligibility criteria)
- **Access:** Institutional access via IP, proxy or institutional email authentication, allowing unlimited multi-user streaming and full-text access

3. Pricing & Invoicing, see Annex

- **Price Structure:** Institutions receive a 25% consortium discount off the standard JOMI price tiers, determined by size (e.g. student/body count or FTE for hospitals)
- **Annual Price Increases:** Maximum 3% per annum, subject to review
- **Invoicing:** JOMI confirms that Otto Harrassowitz GmbH & Co. KG will be invoiced in EUR. Otto Harrassowitz GmbH & Co. KG will issue invoices in EUR for all German consortium participants.

4. Responsibilities

JOMI:

- Provide a registration form (“Beitrittserklärung”) as requested by ZB MED for review
- Delay public webpage publication of the offer until signing of this agreement
- Ensure technical access mechanisms (IP/proxy/email) are fully functional
- permits ZB MED to publish this agreement on platforms such as <https://zenodo.org/> in accordance with data protection regulations.

ZB MED:

- Circulate the registration form (“Beitrittserklärung”) to prospective institutions
- Manage onboarding and enrollment of participating institutions
- Provide consolidated feedback for contract revisions

5. Onboarding and Amendments

- ZB MED may propose amendments to the draft agreement. Final details will be discussed in a dedicated web meeting preceding signature.
- No public promotion of the consortium offer shall occur prior to contract signature.

6. Termination and Join/Exit Options

- Joining: Institutions may join mid-term and will be invoiced pro-rata for the remainder of the calendar year.
- Opt-out: Institutions may withdraw by September 30 in any given year.
- End of Agreement: December 31, 2028, with provision for renewal by mutual written agreement.

7. Legal & IP

- Each party retains ownership of its own pre-existing intellectual property. JOMI grants participating institutions a non-exclusive right to stream and access licensed content for educational purposes.
- Confidential information exchanged between the parties during negotiation and execution shall be governed by mutual confidentiality provisions.

8. Contact and Notices

For **JOMI**: Olivier Diesnis, VP Partnerships (Olivier.Diesnis@jomi.com)

For **ZB MED**: Franziska Fischer, Commercial Director, Notices to Petra Labriga (Labriga@zbmed.de)

Signature Blocks

For ZB MED
Name: Franziska Fischer
Title: Commercial Director
Date: 18.08.2025

For JOMI
Name: Olivier Diesnis
Title: VP Partnerships
Date: 1st August

Annex: Product Sheet